

Data Pitch

H2020-ICT-2016-1

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D7.2 Impact assessment framework

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Introduction

This document details the impact assessment framework to be used in the independent assessment of the Data Pitch programme, which is anticipated in October 2019 at the end of the competitive funding period. This report will help to disseminate the activities of Data Pitch - and the value of cross-sectoral and cross-organisational data sharing - to a business focused audience. The ODI are in discussion with other initiatives to understand what modelling techniques are available or can be designed to evaluate the level of impact innovation is having across various industries within the UK. The assessor may consider drawing upon these techniques to outline a well-established methodology for representing the impact that can be realised over time from innovation programmes such as Data Pitch.

Overview of Data Pitch

Data Pitch is a EU-funded open innovation programme bringing together corporate and public-sector organisations that have data with startups and SMEs that work with data. It is centred around a competition with several tracks, which describe challenges set by the data-provisioning organisations, and an accelerator programme (6 months) to help startups and SMEs develop solutions to meet these challenges.

The startups and SMEs will put forward proposals for creating high impact, innovative products and services in response to the challenges defined by Data Pitch. Successful applicants will receive an important financial and advisory boost to their idea, with support to develop a concept into a robust and sustainable data business. Data Pitch is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, and is being delivered by the University of Southampton, Open Data Institute, Beta-i and Dawex¹.

The programme consists of two calls. The first call opened at 12 noon on the 1st July 2017 and closed at 12 noon on the 1st of October 2017. The second call will be launched on the 2nd July 2018 until 2nd October 2018. Both calls will include three tracks of challenges for startups to address, these are:

- Track 1: Data provider challenges
- Track 2: Sector challenges
- Track 3: Open innovation challenge

Each challenge can be addressed via the use of one or more datasets, open, shared or closed. Each challenge is accompanied by examples of expected outcomes and impacts. Applications must target one challenge only, and explain how it will address it.

Track 1: Data Provider challenges

Challenges are linked to specific datasets, which are provided by European businesses. The applicants must propose a solution that is relevant to the business problem and interests of the data provider. This solution must use the data mentioned in the challenge, possibly in combination with other datasets. Applicants must explain in their application how their idea is compliant with the data terms of use and, if applicable, relevant data protection regulations.

Track 2: Sector challenges

¹ Guide for applicants: https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B9IIZV_CjqLcOTVIYkh6V0xGNE0/view?pli=1

We grouped challenges from sectors that are very important for the EU economy. These challenges have been created via a public consultation and do not refer to any specific, closed datasets. In this case, the applicant is expected to identify the relevant datasets in their applications, and explain how they're accessing at least one critical closed, third-party data resource makes their business idea possible. We would like to add that Data Pitch is an innovation programme exploring the potential of shared datasets for the EU data economy - applications using only open data or third-party data sourced by non-EU data providers will not be considered. Just like in the previous case, applicants will be asked to explain how their idea is compliant with the data terms of use and, if applicable, data protection regulations.

Track 3: Open innovation challenge

We offer a platform for groundbreaking ideas that do not fit in the other tracks of the 2017 and 18 call. This is not a track for incremental ideas. Instead, it provides an opportunity for startups and SMEs that are working on something truly transformative; that can be applied over a wide range of industries; and has the potential to totally reinvent a process or find a solution for a previously unsolvable problem. This means that in track 3 we will consider only those applications that are real game changers, with high impact, that clearly unlock unrealised value in data and can articulate that value in a meaningful way.

Definition of problem

The role of data has transitioned from supporting business decisions to becoming a product or commodity in itself. Data is creating value within Europe's economy and has become critical to its growth in recent years. However, Europe's data economy is not achieving the same level of growth when compared to the US and Asia. Data Pitch has been established to address this gap by creating a transnational data innovation ecosystem within Europe. This innovation ecosystem will enable large corporates and public sector organisations who own data, to collaborate with startups and SME's that have developed innovative data driven products. These collaborations will look to foster to overcome industry specific challenges².

² Grant Agreement number: 732506 — Data Pitch — H2020-ICT-2016-2017/H2020-ICT-2016-1

The Assessment

The assessment is expected to take place within the final year of the programme with the call for tender being released in August 2019. This assessment will follow the final acceleration phase of the Data Pitch startups (September 2019) and will provide partners with an evaluation on how successful the programme has been in achieving its aims, whilst measuring the value and impact generated from the competition winners.

Tender requirements

In order to ensure a unbiased and in-depth assessment of the programme, Data Pitch will commission a tender process, which will be openly available for organisations whom meet the brief specifications. The tender will request applicants to articulate the methods and approach taken to conduct this assessment. Applicants will be expected to highlight how they will utilise the research and data already collected through the life of the programme, in their assessment approach.

Assessment outputs

The results of the assessment will be presented as an impact study report. This report will be used to determine the success of the overall programme. The expected report format is provided in the section labeled 'Assessment report format'.

Report content

An integrated report will include sufficient information on each of the focus/scope elements outlined later in the document, to answer the respective question on how successful the the approach and outcomes of the programme have become. The scope and focus elements are fundamentally linked to each other and should be presented in the integrated report in a way that makes the interconnections between them apparent, rather than as isolated, standalone sections.

Furthermore, to help the programme understand the changes in impact over time, the report will also look to provide

- full transparency of the examined problem,
- details of the stakeholders and domain experts involved to ensure a validated understanding of the results,
- an assessment against the programme KPIs to differentiate between organisation, industry and economic level impacts³.

We have identified and proposed an initial report structure in Annex 2, that can be the basis for the report. Evaluators are able to consider alternative structures, where relevant in their proposals.

Assessment framework

Focus and scope

The assessment will detail;

1. **Analysis of the competition approach**
 - a. **including the inputs, processes, output and outcomes of the competition -**

³ Grant Agreement number: 732506 — Data Pitch — H2020-ICT-2016-2017/H2020-ICT-2016-1

referred from reports/research - no additional research required

2. **Insights: Data provider challenges (track 1) vs Sectoral challenges (track 2)**- referred to from reports - May require some additional research
3. **Impacts on the triple bottom line** (economical, environmental, social) - Research into the wider impacts that have been, or are expected.

Inputs, processes, outputs and outcomes

The assessment will cover, as defined by the Data Pitch grant agreement⁴ the various programme activities and their approach. This section will specifically focus on evaluating the success of the inputs, processes, outputs and outcomes of these activities.

1. inputs (public and private funding received, broken down per individual partners, in-kind contributions etc.);
2. process (mainly related to the organisation of the competitive call, using measures outlined in the project proposal, including the efficacy of the accelerator);
3. output (number of participants to the call, number of challenges funded and number of data providers engaged, by challenge track)
4. outcomes (success of the experiments, summary of products and services developed by the startups and SMEs, reported by challenge track)

Inputs

The startups and SME's that have been successful competition winners and have been awarded funding by Data Pitch, will be evaluated on a case by case basis. Additional research will recognise the value achieved during the acceleration period from further public and private funding received, revenue generated and the number of jobs created. These inputs will add to the assessment and impact of the programme

Data Pitch offers successful startups the opportunity to benefit from in-kind contributions supplied by corporate partners. A comparison can be made to determine if there is a correlation between the inputs and startup success.

Process

In order to generate key recommendations and to understand the lessons learned during the programme, it will be crucial to know for future programmes how successful the process of running the acceleration has been. Specifically looking at the challenge design process and the competitive call, we (the partners) would like to determine if its process was relevant, competitive, fair and resulted in funding the most suitable startups to achieve the programme aims.

Outputs

The assessment may look to understand the value that has been created on the wider European economy from engaging with and securing partnership from the data providers. The report may consider the number of applicants that have applied/been funded, as well as the relevant and most successful challenge tracks that were funded, to understand if more value was created from a collaborative approach to solving challenges.

Outcomes

The outcomes should reflect on the success of the experiments - the products and services

⁴ Grant Agreement number: 732506 — Data Pitch — H2020-ICT-2016-2017/H2020-ICT-2016-1

developed by the startups and SME's in the lab and consider the likelihood of these products and services becoming sustainable with evidence to support this.

Furthermore, the success and outcomes of the experiments should highlight whether there have been any changes in the data sharing mentality of the large corporates and public sector organisations that have participated in the programme.

Insights of Data challenges

Data Provider Challenges - Insights

The programme has underpinned the need to engage with large corporates and public sector organisations to share data for open innovation. In order to determine the value and impact on the data sharing economy, the assessment should investigate;

- the success of the data provider engagement
- the relevance/appropriateness of the selection criteria for applicants,
- the influence of General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) on identifying, accessing and using relevant data sets
- achievements of milestones and success criteria
- the relationship between the data providers and the competition winners, including the role the provider has played in the success achieved by the startup/SME during the acceleration.
- the challenges faced by partners in securing data providers and should discuss recommendations for future similar programmes.

Sectoral Challenges insights

The section above detailed the facts - outputs and outcomes within the sector challenges, this section intends to take a deeper look to identify the strengths and challenges in the sector approach. This should cover the process to select sectors, the relevance and appropriateness of the selection criteria for applicants. The assessor should consider the following:

- achievements of milestones and success criteria
- challenges faced by the startups
- the influence of the GDPR on identifying, accessing and using relevant data sets
- networking, marketing and investment opportunities from within the sector.

Sectoral challenges vs data provider challenges

Following the evaluation of both challenge tracks, the assessment could look to compare the success of both types of challenges to determine which method was more effective in providing value to both industry and the data economy. The evaluation should look into comparing the challenges faced by the partners in designing and acquiring challenges and should look at external factors such as the implementation of the (GDPR) that may have influenced the decision making process.

Impacts on the triple bottom line

Economic impact

The assessment will look at the level of economic impact generated from the competition winners.

This impact will be measured in terms of further investment achieved, revenue generated and the number of jobs created. These values will be compared with the original funding awarded from the programme, to determine the return on investment. The assessor should provide evidence by:

- (quantitative data) Reporting on achievements vs planned values for the indicators (Annex 2) that relate to economic impact.
- (qualitative data) Providing a narrative summary of economic impact achieved by the programme, which may be wider than those captured in the indicators or explore the topic in a greater depth highlighting differences (e.g. between tracks) or contributing factors.

Social Impact

Startups should be assessed in terms of their social impact, to understand the social benefits created through the programme. This assessment can illustrate how sharing data can create social benefits to the European community, as well as the large corporates and public sector organisation that participated in sharing data. The assessment should also consider the possibility of the contribution to social policy change that has been achieved by funded startups, and where possible, provide evidence by:

- (quantitative data) Reporting on achievements vs planned values for the indicators (Annex 2) that relate to social impact (If applicable).
- (qualitative data) Providing a narrative summary of social impact achieved by the programme, which may be wider than those captured in the indicators or explore the topic in a greater depth highlighting differences (e.g. between tracks) or contributing factors (If applicable).

Environmental impact

Startups should be assessed in terms of their environmental impact, to understand the benefits to the environment through the multiple products or services funded by Data Pitch. The assessment should consider the possibility of the contribution to Environmental policy change that has been achieved by the funded startups, and where possible, provide evidence of this by:

- (quantitative data) Reporting on achievements vs planned values for the indicators (Annex 2) that relate to environmental impact (If applicable).
- (qualitative data) Providing a narrative summary of environmental impact achieved by the programme, which may be wider than those captured in the indicators or explore the topic in a greater depth highlighting differences (e.g. between tracks) or contributing factors (If applicable).

Counterfactual scenario

The assessment should explore the possibility of a comparison between funded programme startups from both cohorts, against those of similar value proposition, whom were unsuccessful in being awarded funding through the programme. The comparison will add further evidence to similar future programmes being commissioned due to their impact and the opportunities they create. Indicators such as those related to further investment attained can provide a valued comparison indicator.

Reflection and key recommendations

The assessment should look to provide recommendations to policy makers the European Commission and future innovation programmes on how to successfully run a similar model. The report should describe certain challenges that have been faced, with suggestions on how they could be overcome and highlight driving factors that have led to success.

Furthermore, the report should aim to discuss the benefits that can be attained through the process of sharing data and how these benefits can be valuable for large and public sector organisations, including the wider economy.

Annex 1: Assessment report Format

The report is expected to include the following sections:

Section	
Contents	
Problem definition	
Analysis of the competition approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inputs ● Process ● Outputs ● Outcomes
Sectoral challenges and data provider challenges	
Impacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Economic ● Social ● Environmental
Counterfactuals	
Reflections and recommendations	

Table 1: Assessment report format

Data Pitch will also consider additional content and structure suggestions where relevant.

Annex 2: Expected Impacts

2. IMPACT

2.1. *Expected impacts*

2.1.1. INDICATORS

Shared/closed data providers joining Data Pitch	50
Shared/closed datasets hosted by the lab	75
Sectors covered by our data catalogue	15
Applications for experiments	1000
Companies incubated	50-100
Size of investors network	50
Share of startups/SMEs securing VC investment	10%
Total value unlocked	400%
Annual increase in # of Big Data Value use cases	30%
More investment by data providers to scale industrial data operations	300%
More revenue by EU companies from integrated data & data integration services by 2020	20%

2.1.2. STRATEGIC IMPACT AND STAKEHOLDER GROUPS

2.2. *Measures to maximize impact*

2.2.1 INDICATORS

Participants in information campaign, webinars, peer networking events, datathons	5K
Peer networking events organised	10
Events attended by the Data Pitch team (invited talks, promotion of the call)	50
Size of community (Twitter followers, mailing list subscribers, bloggers)	10K
Companies receiving information about the call	300K
Competitive call promotion reach	3M
Media coverage (editorials and clippings)	100
Articles on data economy microsite	70
Press releases	10
Blog posts, tweets	3K

2.2.2. STRATEGIC IMPACT AND STAKEHOLDER GROUPS